

STEROID COMPOUNDS. PART V. TRICYCLIC INTERMEDIATES FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF D-HOMOSTEROIDS *

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From 1-methylcyclohexane-2:6-dione and the Mannich base from γ -acetobutyric acid, the tricyclic derivatives (IX and X) have been synthesised.

In Part I of this series (Mukharji, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 91) the synthesis of the bicyclic keto-ester (II) was described, and this was in one step converted into the tricyclic ketone (III). A simplified synthesis of compounds of the type (II) in proper stereoisomeric form was warranted in order that the method might be of any practical value in steroid synthesis. In the same paper it was indicated that the Mannich base, ethyl 6-diethylamino-4-ketohexan-1-carboxylate, would be a very useful intermediate in this respect.

A programme of research in this direction was therefore undertaken in 1949, and the first objective was achieved by the preparation of the Mannich base, ethyl 6-piperidino-4-ketohexan-1-carboxylate, (XV) (Chaudhuri and Mukharji, *ibid.*, 1952, 29, 336). The attempted condensation of this Mannich base with 2-methylcyclopentanone in presence of basic catalysts (cf. Du Feu, McQuillin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53; McQuillin and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1938 1097) gave disappointing results, whereas with the sodio derivatives of β -keto-esters like cyclopentanone- and cyclohexanone-2-carboxylates, the reaction proceeded very smoothly and the condensation products in each case were obtained in excellent yields (cf. Wilds and Shunk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 469).

We accordingly turned our attention to a study of the reaction of the above Mannich base with 1-methylcyclohexane-2:6-dione (IV: Blaise Maire, *Compt. rend.*, 1907, 144, 573). Several factors influenced this decision. Firstly, it was more readily accessible than the corresponding cyclopentane analogue, 1-methylcyclopentane-2:5-dione, and being a β -diketone was expected to react in yields comparable with β -keto-esters. Secondly, we argued that since decalin was stable in the *trans* configuration, reduction of the double bond in (VI) in contrast to systems like (I) under suitable conditions would produce at least a mixture of the *cis* and *trans* forms in which the latter might predominate. The reverse ratio of isomers could be expected in the reduction of the system (I) because of the greater stability of *cis*-hydrindane. To establish *trans* locking at this stage was essential for the ultimate success of the scheme.

While the work with 1-methylcyclohexane-2:6-dione was in progress, Wieland *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 36, 377) quite independently, and perhaps unaware of our previous publications, published an account of their work which was essentially identical with ours in the general approach and differed only in the detail of execution. A preliminary note of our work had already been published (*Science & Culture*, 1953,

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18, 602; 1954, 19, 463). Because the variants employed by us were an improvement over their method and since some of the intermediate compounds had been more fully characterised by us, the publication of this complete report was considered desirable.

In the beginning we tried condensation of the methiodide of the base (XV) with the sodio derivative of 1-methylcyclohexane-2:6-dione under conditions described by Wilds and Shunk (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3956). The reaction product was an acid (m.p. 142°) and very little neutral material was formed. Under identical conditions we found that the methiodide of diethylaminobutanone furnished an acid of m.p. 46-47° almost exclusively. After we had carried out these experiments, Wendler, Slates and Tishler (*ibid.*, 1951, 73, 3816) published an account of their work and confirmed the structure (XI) for the acid, m.p. 46-47°. Our acid of m.p. 142° ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 250 m μ) was found to be dibasic and presumably arose through the same process with concomitant hydrolysis of the primary ester group. No attempts were made to establish the constitution of this acid to which structure (XII) has been assigned on the basis of analogy.

When a mixture of the free base and the dione was refluxed in benzene solution with a little piperidine or trimethylamine, an oily neutral material was obtained, although in low yields, but no acidic product was formed under these conditions. When pyridine was added to the above mixture, the yield of the neutral condensation product improved remarkably (Howe *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1945, 67, 381; Friedman and Robinson, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1951, 777; Newman, referred in the latter paper). Robinson and Newman used the above conditions to prepare the diketone (XIII) from 1-methylcyclohexane-2:6-dione and diethylaminobutanone. The oily distillate from the condensation of the base (XV) with the dione was obtained in about 50-55% yield and consisted mostly of the triketo-ester (V). This distillate had a maxima at 250m μ in the ultraviolet ($\log \epsilon$ 3.1) showing that only partial ring-closure had taken place in contrast to the case of diethylaminobutanone under identical conditions. This was, however, not very surprising considering the decreased acidity of hydrogen in -CO-CH₂- compared to CO-CH₃. Ring-closure of the triketo compound to the bicyclic eneone (VI) could be effected by refluxing with aluminium *tert.*-butoxide in benzene solution (Wayne and Adkins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 3401; Wendler, Slates and Tishler, *loc. cit.*) or by refluxing with piperidine acetate in benzene (Kuhn, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 98). Yields were roughly 25-30% in either case, although with the latter reagent a much cleaner product could be obtained. Wieland *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) cyclised the same compound by refluxing with a mixture of triethylamine and benzoic acid in xylene solution, but did not report the yield. The bicyclic compound (VI) had the expected spectral properties and was further characterised by a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 185-86°. Catalytic reduction of the double bond and hydrolysis of the resulting dihydro derivative (VII) afforded a gummy acid mixture from which two crystalline acids, m.p. 133-34° (VIIIa) and m.p. 121-24° (VIIIb) could be isolated (cf. Wieland *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

For the elaboration of the third ring, we selected a method which was different from the Swiss procedure and had the advantage that the transformation could be

effected in only two steps and without isolation of the intermediates. The overall yield was also very good. The Swiss procedure required five to six steps for the same conversion. The diketone, m.p. 133-34° (VIIIa) was refluxed with acetic anhydride and acetyl chloride to furnish the enol-lactone enol-acetate (XVII) which was obtained as an oil. This was next treated with the Grignard reagent from ethylmagnesium bromide, and the crude reaction product cyclised to the tricyclic diketone (IX) which could be directly obtained crystalline. After purification, this had m. p. 135-36° ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$ 250 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.23; bands at 5.84 μ , 6.0 μ and 6.2 μ in the infra-red). This method is analogous to the procedure of Fujimoto for the synthesis of progesterone labelled at C₄ position. (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3259). Reduction of the above diketone with sodium borohydride in alcohol yielded the corresponding diol which in the crude stage was oxidised with manganese dioxide in chloroform (Sondheimer, Amendolla and Rosenkranz, *Exper.*, 1953, 9, 62; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5930) to the hydroxy-eneone (X), m.p. 132-33° ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$ 250 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.13; bands at 2.8 μ , 6.0 μ and 6.2 μ in the infra-red). The physical and spectral properties agree in all respects with the values reported by Wieland *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) for the diketone and the hydroxy-eneone prepared by them from the bicyclic acid, m.p. 133-34°. In view of the publications by the Swiss chemists our experiments with the isomeric acid, m.p. 123-24°, were not pursued.

The configuration of the tricyclic diketone, m.p. 135-36° (IX) had been firmly established by the Swiss chemists (Wieland, Anner and Miescher, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 36, 646) which they later utilised for the total synthesis of D-homosteroids (Wieland, Uberwasser, Anner and Miescher, *ibid.*, 1953, 36, 1231). The variants described by us in the present communication make available the above tricyclic compounds (IX and X), and hence, the D-homosteroids by one of the shortest routes so far described to synthesise steroids.

The condensation of the methiodide of diethylaminobutanone with the sodio derivative of 1-methylcyclohexane-2:6-dione in presence of aluminium *tert.*-butoxide in methanol-benzene mixture afforded mostly neutral material from which the desired diketone (XIII) could be obtained by chromatography; formation of acidic material was practically negligible, although the yield of the diketone was not very encouraging. The pyridine method has been described since no details have been published so far.

In the preparation of the Mannich base (XV; Chaudhuri and Mukharji, *loc. cit.*) further improvement in the yield has been effected by working up the mother-liquors left after removal of the crystalline base hydrochloride (XIV). We have used a revised nomenclature for this base (XV) in the present paper because the one used in our earlier publication is apt to be confusing.

After our paper on the above Mannich base had been published, Nazarov and Zavyalov (*Chem. Abs.*, 1953, 47, 5364) described that the product obtained by heating γ -acetobutyric acid with paraformaldehyde and dimethylamine hydrochloride, or esterification with methanolic hydrogen chloride, followed by basification with

potassium carbonate, yielded an unsaturated keto-ester, which on oxidation with nitric acid furnished succinic acid. On the basis of this they concluded that the reaction with paraformaldehyde had occurred at the methylene position, and they assigned structure (XVI) to their unsaturated ester. This is contrary to our observations, unless the change of the base hydrochloride, employed, in some peculiar way influences the reaction path, and this from all considerations appears very unlikely. We had no difficulty in obtaining the crystalline base hydrochloride (XIV) as well as the ethyl ester of the base (XV), which also analysed well. The structure of our product was very convincingly proved by conversion into δ -ketoazelic acid. We are of the opinion that the oxidation with nitric acid, which the Russian chemists used, is somewhat too drastic and the possibility of further oxidation of glutaric acid to succinic acid under such conditions cannot be entirely ruled out.

(XVII)

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

(XIV)

(XV)

(XVI)

EXPERIMENTAL

Methylcyclohexane-2:6-dione (IV) was best prepared by cyclisation of ethyl 4-ketohexane-1-carboxylate with alcohol-free sodium ethoxide in dry ether, initially at room temperature for about 3 hours, followed by reflux for another hour. An average yield was about 20 g. of dione from 34 g. of the keto-ester, m.p. 208-209°; lit. reports m.p. 210° (Blaise Maire, *loc. cit.*).

Ethyl 6-Piperidino-4-ketohexan-1-carboxylate (XV) was prepared as described in our previous communication (Chaudhuri and Mukharji, *loc. cit.*). A mixture of γ -acetobutyric acid (39 g.), piperidine hydrochloride (36.5 g.) and paraformaldehyde (9 g.) furnished on an average about 34-35 g. of the crystalline base hydrochloride, m.p. 158-59°, which was then converted into the above ethyl ester in the usual way.

However, considerable quantities of the base hydrochloride remained in alcohol-acetone solution which could not be recovered by direct crystallisation. The following procedure resulted in a fair recovery of the base as its ethyl ester. The alcohol-acetone solution obtained after removal of the crystalline base hydrochloride was completely evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the brown gummy residue esterified with 3% ethanolic hydrogen chloride. Excess of alcohol was then removed under reduced pressure. The residual viscous mass was dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and extracted three times with ether to remove the unchanged keto-acid. The aqueous solution was then carefully basified and the liberated Mannich base ethyl ester isolated by repeated ether extractions and purified by distillation. The structure of this product was also settled by conversion into δ -ketoazelic acid.

Condensation of Ethyl 6-Piperidino-4-ketohexan-1-carboxylate with 1-Methyl-cyclohexane-2:6-dione: Formation of 1-Methyl-1-(3'-keto-6-carbethoxyhexyl)-cyclohexane-2:6-dione (V)

(a). To a solution of sodium methoxide in anhydrous methanol, obtained from metallic sodium (1.2 g.) and methyl alcohol (30 c.c.), the *cyclohexan-dione* (6.3 g.) was added and left at room temperature to obtain a clear solution. It was then cooled in ice and a solution of the methiodide of ethyl 6-piperidino-4-ketohexan-1-carboxylate, prepared from the base (15 g.), in absolute methyl alcohol was added. After allowing it to remain at this temperature for about 3 hours, it was left at room temperature overnight. Next day it was heated on a steam-bath for about an hour, then cooled and poured into ice containing some hydrochloric acid. The resulting solution was then saturated with ammonium chloride and extracted several times with ether. The ether extract was then washed with ice-cold 5% sodium bicarbonate solution until the aqueous extract was alkaline to litmus. The ether solution was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated. The oil left on removal of the ether distilled at 170°-195°/1 mm. and a portion of this distillate solidified. This was identified as the unchanged dione, m.p. 208-209°. The remainder of the oil (about 1.0 g.) did not furnish any solid derivative and was not further investigated.

The bicarbonate extract was acidified with ice-cooling and the precipitated acid obtained as silky needles was collected by filtration and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 141-42°. This acid is soluble in hot water, but sparingly so in cold water. From potentiometric titration it was found to be dibasic. $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 250 μ ; log ϵ , 4.14. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 7.61. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 62.68; H, 7.46 per cent).

(b). A mixture of 1-methyl*cyclohexan-2:6-dione* (12.6 g.), ethyl 6-piperidino-4-ketohexan-1-carboxylate (30 g.), dry pyridine (10 c.c.) and benzene (100 c.c.) was heated under reflux for five hours. The reaction mixture was then cooled and acidified with ice and HCl. The unchanged dione separating was removed by filtration. The benzene layer was then separated and the aqueous layer once extracted with ether and the extract combined with the first benzene extract. The combined solution was then washed with cold 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, cold dilute HCl solution and finally with water. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residual oil distilled. After a small forerun of the low boiling material, the oily product distilling over at 185°-190°/1 mm. was collected, yield 12 g. (53% based on reacted dione). This distillate had $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 250 μ (log ϵ , 3.1) showing that partial ring-closure had taken place during condensation. Attempts to purify the adduct by redistillation almost in every case produced some *cyclohexan-dione*, possibly by reversal of the Michael at elevated temperature. The adduct, however, very readily furnished a trisemicarbazone which after crystallisation from a large volume of alcohol had m.p. 203°-209°, depending on the rate of heating. (Found: C, 48.58; H, 7.2; N, 27.36. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires C, 48.82; H, 7.07; N, 26.98 per cent). The bicarbonate extract on acidification yielded the dibasic acid, m.p. 141-42° in about 5% yield.

9-Methyl-4-(β -carbethoxyethyl)- Δ^4 -octalin-3:8-dione (VI).—(a). The above triketo-ester (7.4 g.) and aluminium *tert.*-butoxide (8 g.) in dry benzene were refluxed for 40 hours under nitrogen. The reaction mixture was then cooled, decomposed with ice and HCl and the organic layer separated. The aqueous layer was extracted once more with ether and the ether extract combined with the first benzene extract. The combined extract was washed with water and carefully decanted off from the tarry matter that had separated; after washing with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and with water, this was dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residual viscous oil distilled at 170°-180°/1 mm. which on redistillation boiled at 172-75°/1 mm., yield 1.8 g. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 250 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.15. (Found: C, 68.52; H, 8.3. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 69.06; H, 7.91 per cent). This enedione furnished a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone which after three crystallisations from ethyl acetate had m.p. 185-86°. (Found: C, 52.41; H, 4.85; N, 17.45. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_8$ requires C, 52.66; H, 4.7; N, 17.53 per cent).

(b). The triketo-ester (7.4 g.) was heated with a mixture of piperidine (2.1 g.) and glacial acetic acid (3 c.c.) in benzene (40 c.c.) in a flask fitted with a Dean-Stark water separator. After reflux for 40 hours under nitrogen, the reaction product was worked up as described above. The distillate (2 g.), b.p. 172°-176°/1 mm. had identical ultraviolet absorption spectra as above and also furnished the same 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

9-Methyl-1:6-diketodecalin-5- β -propionic Acid (VIIIa & VIIIb).—The unsaturated compound (VI, 10 g.), obtained above, in ethanol (15 c.c.) was reduced at room temperature with hydrogen in presence of 10% Pd-C (0.5 g.). In about 10 hours the theoretical amount of hydrogen was absorbed. The catalyst was filtered off, the solvent removed and the dihydro derivative (VII) purified by distillation, b.p. 170-72°/1 mm., yield 9 g. This distillate did not show any absorption around 250 m μ in the ultraviolet.

This reduced product (8 g.) in methanol (35 c.c.) was treated with 5% NaOH solution (30 c.c.), left at room temperature for about 90 minutes and then it was heated for a short period at 80°, treated with a few drops of HCl (dil.) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was acidified with cooling and the organic matter taken up in chloroform. The gummy acid left on removal of the chloroform was dissolved in dry ether and on allowing it to stand for some time a portion of the gum crystallised. These were filtered off, washed with cold dry ether and had m.p. 129-32°. After two crystallisations from ether this had m.p. 134-35°, yield 3.4 g. (Found: C, 66.21; H, 7.75. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 66.67; H, 7.91 per cent). From the mother-liquors it was somewhat difficult to obtain a pure specimen of the other isomer directly, although a few crystals could be obtained. The gum therefore was re-esterified, sublimed and hydrolysed as described above. The resulting gummy acid was dissolved in a mixture of acetone and ether and cooled when some crystals appeared. After a second crystallisation from acetone-ether mixture it had m.p. 123-24°, yield 1.5 g.

1:7-Diketo-8:11-dimethyl- $\Delta^{3:14}$ -dodecahydrophenanthrene (IX).—The acid of m.p. 134-35° (2.5 g.), acetic anhydride (12 c.c.) and acetyl chloride (12 c.c.) were refluxed under nitrogen for about 50 hours. The low boiling materials were then carefully removed under diminished pressure and the residue sublimed when a viscous oil came over at 180°-185°/1 mm., yield 1.8 g. This oily enol-lactone enol-acetate (XVII) did not solidify on standing or on trituration with solvents.

The above enol-lactone enol-acetate (1.7 g.) in dry ether (80 c.c.) was cooled in ice-salt mixture and ethylmagnesium bromide, prepared from magnesium (0.2 g.) and ethyl bromide (0.6 g.) in ether (25 c.c.), was added with stirring. A curdy white precipitate was obtained. At the end of the addition, the mixture was slowly allowed to attain room temperature and left as such overnight. It was then decomposed with a cold solution of ammonium chloride and the organic layer separated; the aqueous layer was extracted three times with ether and combined with the first ether extract and then concentrated. The residue left after removal of the ether was treated with glacial acetic acid (32 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 3 c.c.) and left in an atmosphere of nitrogen at room temperature for 48 hours. It was then all but completely evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was then washed with cold dilute NaOH solution, water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On allowing the ether to evaporate slowly, crystals were deposited which were collected by filtration. This crude diketone had m.p. 128-31° and was slightly coloured. A benzene solution of the compound was passed through a small amount of alumina and the crystals from this were recrystallised from dry ether, m.p. 135-36°, yield 0.6 g. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 250 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.23; bands at 5.84 μ , 6.0 μ and 6.2 μ in the infra-red. (Found: C, 77.82; H, 9.12. C₁₆H₂₂O₂ requires C, 78.05; H, 8.94 per cent).

1-Hydroxy-7-keto-8:11-dimethyl- $\Delta^{3:14}$ -dodecahydrophenanthrene (X).—The above diketone (300 mg.) in alcohol (2-3 c.c.) was added to a solution of sodium borohydride (500 mg.) in 70% ethyl alcohol (10 c.c.) with ice-cooling and then allowed to attain room temperature and left as such overnight. Next morning the solution was evaporated to dryness, diluted with water and extracted several times with chloroform. The residue from chloroform was an amorphous mass which did not show any absorption around 250 m μ in the ultraviolet. Bands around 5.84 μ and 6.0 μ in the infra-red were also absent. This amorphous material in chloroform (7-10 c.c.) was stirred overnight with manganese dioxide (200 mg.) at room temperature. The oxide was then filtered off, washed with several portions of hot chloroform and the total chloroform extracts were combined and concentrated. The gummy residue was dissolved in dry benzene and passed through a short column of alumina and concentrated. The resulting crystalline product was crystallised from benzene-petrol ether mixture, m.p. 132-33°; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 250 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.1; bands at 2.8 μ , 6.0 μ and 6.2 μ in the infra-red. (Found: C, 77.13; H, 9.72. C₁₆H₂₄O₂ requires C, 77.42; H, 9.68 per cent).

Condensation of 1-Methylcyclohexane-2:6-dione with Diethylaminobutanone

(a). The dione (6.3 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (1.2 g.) in methanol (30 c.c.) and left for some time. It was then cooled in ice and a methanolic solution

of the methoiodide of diethylaminobutanone, prepared from the base (10 g.), was slowly added. The mixture was left overnight and then refluxed for 1 hour, cooled and worked up in the usual way and separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The neutral fraction distilled over a range of 120° - 135° /1 mm. and the yield was about 2.0 g. No solid derivatives could be prepared from this fraction. (Found: C, 65.69; H, 8.38 per cent).

The acidic portion, which was obtained initially as an oil, solidified on distillation, yield 4.0 g., m.p. 46 - 47° ; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 243 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.1. (Found: C, 67.12 H, 8.32. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.35; H, 8.16 per cent.). The semicarbazone after crystallisation from dilute alcohol had m.p. 201 - 203° . (Found: N, 16.84. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 16.6 per cent). The corresponding ethyl ester afforded a red 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 101 - 102° . (Found: N, 14.02. $C_{19}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.86 per cent).

(b) This procedure was exactly as the one above excepting that before the addition of the methoiodide, a solution of aluminium *tert.*-butoxide (10 g.) in dry benzene was added. The reaction mixture was worked up the usual way and separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral portion (about 7 g.) was separated into two fractions by distillation: (i) b.p. 115° - 120° /1 mm., a mobile liquid, 3 g., (ii) b.p. 128° - 132° /1 mm., a somewhat viscous liquid, 3 g. The second fraction was chromatographed over alumina and eluted with a mixture of benzene and ether. The crystalline material thus obtained was recrystallised from ether-petrol ether mixture, m.p. 48 - 49° ; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 244 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.08. (Found: C, 73.85; H, 8.1. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 74.16; H, 7.86 per cent). Yield of the crystalline product was about 2 g. The *bis*-semicarbazone was crystallised from alcohol and then had m.p. 244 - 45° (Found: N, 29.08., $C_{13}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires N, 28.77 per cent).

The first fraction of the distillate did not solidify and also did not afford any crystalline derivative.

(c). A mixture of the dione (6.3 g.) diethylaminobutanone (7.5 g.), dry pyridine (5 c.c.) and benzene (50 c.c.) was refluxed for about 6 hours in a flask fitted with a Dean-Stark water separator. The mixture was then cooled and poured into a mixture of ice and HCl. It was then filtered from a precipitate (about 1.3 g.) which was the unchanged dione. The aqueous solution was removed and extracted with ether and this extract was then mixed with the original benzene solution. The combined extract was then washed with cold 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water and finally concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue left after removal of the solvent distilled at 128° - 130° /1 mm. and the distillate solidified on scratching. It was recrystallised from ether-petrol ether mixture, m.p. 48 - 49° , yield 3.5 g. The *bis*-semicarbazone had m.p. 244 - 45° and identical with the sample obtained above.

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